

The Effect of Organizational Culture on the Intentions to Embrace Environmental Sustainability Practices in Egypt

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Abstract:

This study explores the impact of organizational culture on the intentions to embrace environmental sustainability practices within Egyptian corporations, providing insights into the cultural drivers that facilitate or impede sustainable business practices. Using a quantitative approach, the research employs correlation and regression analyses to examine the relationships between various dimensions of organizational culture including environmental values, cultural norms, top management support, vision and mission alignment, involvement in sustainability, training and awareness programs, internal communication, transparency and reporting, sustainability departments, integration into business units, sustainability policies, and operational practices. and their influence on sustainability intentions. Data were collected through structured surveys distributed among professionals in various industries across Egypt. The findings reveal significant positive correlations between all measured aspects of organizational culture and the intentions to adopt sustainability practices. Particularly strong influences were noted from factors such as sustainability policies, top management support, and integration into business units, which were found to substantially drive the intentions towards sustainability.

Keywords: Organizational Culture, Environmental Sustainability, Sustainability Practices, Leadership Commitment, Corporate Strategy, Cultural Dimensions, Sustainability Policies and Sustainable Development.

Introduction

In the evolving business landscape, the influence of organizational culture on embracing environmental sustainability practices has garnered significant attention. The complexity of integrating sustainability into corporate strategies presents a distinct challenge, particularly within the context of developing countries like Egypt. This study investigates how various dimensions of organizational culture in Egyptian companies affect their intentions to adopt such practices. By dissecting cultural factors and their interplay with corporate sustainability initiatives, the research aims to shed light on the pathways through which organizational culture can enhance or hinder environmental sustainability.

Literature Review

Deshpande and Webster (1989) established the link between corporate culture and marketing, highlighting how organizational values affect marketing strategies. Their work has informed numerous studies on corporate culture's importance in business scenarios. For instance, Brondoni (2002) emphasized corporate culture's role in managing relationships in large firms amidst globalization. Kvirkvaia and Kikutadze (2014) explored how corporate culture enhances business efficiency by setting value transmission standards. Similarly, Ha et al. (2020) found that corporate culture positively influences trust and repurchase intentions, while Yang (2010) noted its impact on brand culture and customer loyalty. Aligning culture with a company's mission is crucial for sustainable growth, as discussed by Hui et al. (2021). This alignment aids in organizational identity and employee integration, as analyzed by Derhachova and Fedirko (2018).

The work of Hofstede and Minkov (2010) on cultural dimensions theory has significantly impacted the understanding of cultural differences and organizational behavior. Their framework, which extends Hofstede's model, provides insights into how culture affects human activity. Abdelrahim (2021) suggested adding tribalism as a new dimension to the theory. Kasatkin (2017) highlighted values in shaping cultural landscapes, while Moraczewski (2016) examined culture in social heterogeneity. Yildiz (2018) and Sokolov and Alekseev-Apraksin (2019) discussed cultural shifts and clustering of cultural reality, respectively. Jin reflected on the commoditization of culture, and Caetano and Bezzi (2011) emphasized cultural codes in geography. Flier (2020) described culture as organized values influencing worldviews, and Gurova (2023) noted shifts toward spiritual values in cultural production.

Epstein and Buhovac (2014) emphasized integrating ESG criteria into corporate performance metrics. Their work has influenced studies on sustainability assessment and management. Gutterman (2020) stressed robust controls in CSR strategic planning, broadening assessments beyond financial metrics. Kasim et al. (2018) explored sustainability strategies in Malaysia, while Kassahun highlighted enterprise systems' role in sustainability measurement. Arora (2015) proposed a balanced scorecard framework for sustainability performance. Speziale and Klovienė (2014) demonstrated PMS's role in CSR, while Saeed and Kersten (2020) noted gaps in sustainability assessment. Denčić-Mihajlov and Zeranski (2018) focused on sustainable management performance indicators. Turan et al. (2016) introduced a methodology for evaluating sustainability compliance, and Yalçın (2022) studied sustainability's impact on earnings quality.

In "Built to Last," Collins and Porras (1996) examined the success factors of visionary companies, highlighting visionary management's

role in long-term success. These companies align their vision with core values beyond financial performance (Starkey & Tempest, 1996), foster innovation, and create environments encouraging employee engagement (Zien & Buckler, 1996). They outline principles like Level 5 leadership and technology as accelerators (Barbe & Kleiner, 2005), emphasizing adaptability and self-criticism for longevity. This framework influences contemporary management practices.

Daily and Huang (2001) linked HRM with environmental performance, showing how strategic HR practices enhance sustainability. This link is seen in Brazilian companies, where HR practices reduce resource consumption (Freitas et al., 2015). Evaluating managers on environmental goals reinforces positive environmental outcomes (Portocarrero & Winkler, 2021). HRM balances economic, environmental, and social performance, maximizing benefits (Tang et al., 2017). It plays a crucial role in corporate environmental management by enhancing professional and staff awareness (Ma & Wang, 2011).

Jackson et al. (2011) explored Green HRM, emphasizing HR practices' role in supporting sustainability. GHRM includes environmentally friendly activities like reducing waste and promoting technology use (P., 2023). It raises environmental awareness and encourages green practices (Solanki, 2016), helping organizations gain a competitive edge (Soviana et al., 2022). GHRM positively influences innovation and organizational outcomes, enhancing business performance and reducing pollution (Amrutha & Geetha, 2020; Mustafa et al., 2023).

Lozano (2013) emphasized the need for a holistic approach to sustainability, integrating social, environmental, and economic aspects into business operations. Aligning structures and culture with sustainability goals requires organizational change (Gutterman, 2020).

Employees are crucial in implementing sustainable practices (Wolf, 2013). Strategic frameworks integrate economic, environmental, and social factors into decision-making (Garza, 2013). Stakeholder involvement in sustainability accounting is vital for balancing issues and advancing goals (Ionescu, 2016).

Adams and McNicholas (2007) highlighted sustainability reporting's role in driving change. It supports planning and enhances reporting quality (Lozano et al., 2016). Reporting affects reputation based on disclosure quality (Van, 2011). It now includes economic, environmental, and social performance (Mitra & Agarwal, 2012), impacting strategic planning and risk management (Adams & Frost, 2008). Integrated reporting faces challenges with limited disclosure (Stacchezzini et al., 2016). Sustainability reporting creates long-term value, promoting social justice (Godha & Jain, 2015).

Epstein and Roy (2001) focused on sustainability performance measurement and management, integrating it into strategies and operations. PMS supports CSR initiatives and enhances performance (Speziale & Klovienè, 2014). There is a gap in performance assessment quality (Saeed & Kersten, 2020). Systematic assessments like GPM P5 Integration Matrix measure compliance (Turan et al., 2016). Epstein and Roy (2003) identified principles for improving sustainability metrics.

Hart and Milstein (2003) developed the Sustainable Value Framework for creating value through sustainability. It integrates environmental, social, and economic considerations (Patala et al., 2016). Fatemi and Fooladi (2020) discussed models maximizing shareholder wealth without stakeholder impact. Aagaard (2018) provided a framework for sustainable business models, emphasizing value creation, delivery, and capture.

Delmas and Toffel (2008) explored responses to sustainability pressures, emphasizing leadership and market forces. Companies adopt practices like eco-innovation (Paraschiv et al., 2012) and embed sustainability in design (Gutterman, 2020). Employees moderate the link between sustainability implementation and performance (Wolf, 2013). Institutional pressures influence environmental performance, with management accounting mediating effects (Chaudhry & Amir, 2020).

Russo and Fouts (1997) examined environmental performance's impact on profitability, showing enhanced performance reduces costs (Earnhart & Lizal, 2007). Environmental innovation links performance with financial outcomes (Ong et al., 2019). Corporate self-regulation improves customer value (Petrović-Ranđelović et al., 2023).

Eccles et al. (2014) studied sustainability's impact on performance, showing high-sustainability companies outperform others long-term (Eccles et al., 2012). Sustainability practices improve financial returns and investment efficiency (Poursoleyman et al., 2022), emphasizing strategic integration's importance (Engert et al., 2016).

Comment on Literature Review

The literature review presents a comprehensive exploration of various models and theories related to corporate culture, sustainability, and their influence on business practices and performance. The review effectively synthesizes the findings from multiple studies, offering a nuanced understanding of the interplay between corporate culture, sustainability, and organizational success. The review has several positive aspects. Firstly, it covers a wide array of topics, from corporate culture and marketing strategies to sustainability performance measurement and environmental management. This broad scope provides a holistic understanding of the interconnectedness of these

elements within the business context. Additionally, by including studies from different regions and sectors, the review underscores the universal importance of corporate culture and sustainability in various business environments. This diversity enhances the richness of the discussion and demonstrates the global relevance of the topics covered. The review adeptly integrates seminal works, such as those by Deshpande and Webster (1989) and Collins and Porras (1996), with contemporary studies. This balance ensures a comprehensive perspective that acknowledges both foundational theories and modern advancements. Furthermore, the review emphasizes the practical implications of corporate culture and sustainability practices on organizational effectiveness, highlighting their roles in strategic alignment, human resources, and management.

However, there are areas for improvement. The review could benefit from a more critical evaluation of the studies, discussing potential biases, limitations, or methodological weaknesses to add depth to the analysis. It could also delve further into emerging trends and technologies impacting corporate culture and sustainability, such as digital transformation and artificial intelligence, to enhance its relevance in the current business landscape. Although the review covers various themes, it does not explicitly identify gaps in the literature or areas where further research is needed. Articulating these gaps would provide a clearer direction for future studies and highlight unresolved questions in the field. Additionally, there are inconsistencies in how references are cited throughout the review. Ensuring uniformity in reference formatting would improve the document's professionalism and readability.

To build upon the current review, several suggestions for further research can be considered. Investigating how emerging technologies influence corporate culture and sustainability practices could provide valuable insights for adapting these concepts to future business

environments. Conducting long-term studies to assess the impact of sustainability practices on financial performance over time would help validate claims made in the current literature. Comparative studies examining how corporate culture and sustainability practices vary across different cultural contexts could enhance understanding of these concepts globally. Furthermore, further research on the role of leadership in fostering a culture of sustainability could provide actionable insights for organizations seeking to integrate sustainable practices. Overall, the literature review provides a solid foundation for understanding the role of corporate culture and sustainability in business. By incorporating more critical analysis and exploring emerging trends, it could further contribute to the field's development and offer valuable guidance for future research initiatives.

Research Problem:

Environmental sustainability has emerged as a global concern, with businesses playing a crucial role in mitigating environmental impacts. In Egypt, the push for sustainable practices is growing, driven by both global trends and local environmental challenges. However, the role of organizational culture in this transition within Egyptian corporates remains underexplored. This research investigates how organizational culture in Egyptian companies influences their intentions to embrace environmental sustainability practices. Whin in the following objectives:

- To identify key cultural factors within Egyptian organizations that promote or hinder the adoption of sustainability practices.
- To examine the relationship between organizational culture and the intention to implement sustainable practices in Egypt.
- To provide recommendations for fostering a culture that supports environmental sustainability in the Egyptian context.

The Significance of the Study

Understanding the impact of organizational culture on sustainability practices in Egypt can help businesses develop more effective strategies for environmental stewardship. This study contributes to the body of knowledge by providing insights into how cultural dynamics within Egyptian organizations shape sustainability intentions and offering practical recommendations for cultivating a sustainability-oriented culture.

Research Questions:

Q1: What are the main cultural factors influencing corporate intentions toward environmental sustainability in Egypt?

Q2: How does leadership commitment to sustainability affect organizational culture in Egyptian companies?

Q3: What role does employee engagement play in the adoption of sustainable practices in Egypt?

Q4: How do communication and shared values within Egyptian organizations influence sustainability intentions?

Conceptual Framework and hypothesis:

conceptual model is presented to clarify the connection between different aspects of organizational culture and the intention to implement environmental sustainability practices within Egyptian corporations, thereby expanding the current understanding of how organizational culture impacts these initiatives. Key factors such as environmental values and leadership commitment significantly influence how employees perceive the importance and advantages of sustainability efforts. Likewise, the ease of integrating sustainability practices into daily operations, which is affected by elements like internal communication and training programs, impacts the intention to adopt these practices. The theoretical framework establishes links

between these elements of organizational culture and outlines a plan for further research into how these factors influence the adoption of sustainability practices in Egyptian companies. This chapter is built on a comprehensive review of relevant literature, providing a foundation for further study. The reviewed works shed light on the role of organizational culture in environmental sustainability and establish the basis for the conceptual framework that will guide empirical research in subsequent chapters. This approach not only enhances the understanding of the direct impact of organizational culture on sustainability initiatives but also incorporates a wider range of cultural influences, making the analysis more thorough and applicable to the Egyptian corporate setting.

Figure 1, Conceptual Framework

Elaborated by researcher

Hypothesis:

1- Environmental Values

- Null Hypothesis (H0_1): There is no significant relationship between environmental values within an organization and the intentions to embrace environmental sustainability practices in Egyptian enterprises.
- Alternative Hypothesis (H1_1): There is a significant positive relationship between environmental values within an organization and the intentions to embrace environmental sustainability practices in Egyptian enterprises.

2- Cultural Norms

- Null Hypothesis (H0_2): There is no significant relationship between cultural norms promoting sustainability and the intentions to embrace environmental sustainability practices in Egyptian enterprises.
- Alternative Hypothesis (H1_2): There is a significant positive relationship between cultural norms promoting sustainability and the intentions to embrace environmental sustainability practices in Egyptian enterprises.

3- Top Management Support

- Null Hypothesis (H0_3): There is no significant relationship between top management support for sustainability and the intentions to embrace environmental sustainability practices in Egyptian enterprises.
- Alternative Hypothesis (H1_3): There is a significant positive relationship between top management support for sustainability and the intentions to embrace environmental sustainability practices in Egyptian enterprises.

4- Vision and Mission Alignment

- Null Hypothesis (H0_4): There is no significant relationship between the alignment of vision and mission with sustainability principles and the intentions to embrace environmental sustainability practices in Egyptian enterprises.
 - Alternative Hypothesis (H1_4): There is a significant positive relationship between the alignment of vision and mission with sustainability principles and the intentions to embrace environmental sustainability practices in Egyptian enterprises.
- 5- Involvement in Sustainability Initiatives
- Null Hypothesis (H0_5): There is no significant relationship between employee involvement in sustainability initiatives and the intentions to embrace environmental sustainability practices in Egyptian enterprises.
 - Alternative Hypothesis (H1_5): There is a significant positive relationship between employee involvement in sustainability initiatives and the intentions to embrace environmental sustainability practices in Egyptian enterprises.
- 6- Training and Awareness Programs
- Null Hypothesis (H0_6): There is no significant relationship between the provision of sustainability training programs and the intentions to embrace environmental sustainability practices in Egyptian enterprises.
 - Alternative Hypothesis (H1_6): There is a significant positive relationship between the provision of sustainability training programs and the intentions to embrace environmental sustainability practices in Egyptian enterprises.
- 7- Internal Communication
- Null Hypothesis (H0_7): There is no significant relationship between internal communication about sustainability and the intentions to embrace environmental sustainability practices in Egyptian enterprises.

- Alternative Hypothesis (H1_7): There is a significant positive relationship between internal communication about sustainability and the intentions to embrace environmental sustainability practices in Egyptian enterprises.

8- Transparency and Reporting

- Null Hypothesis (H0_8): There is no significant relationship between transparency in sustainability reporting and the intentions to embrace environmental sustainability practices in Egyptian enterprises.
- Alternative Hypothesis (H1_8): There is a significant positive relationship between transparency in sustainability reporting and the intentions to embrace environmental sustainability practices in Egyptian enterprises.

9- Sustainability Departments/Teams

- Null Hypothesis (H0_9): There is no significant relationship between the existence of dedicated sustainability teams or departments and the intentions to embrace environmental sustainability practices in Egyptian enterprises.
- Alternative Hypothesis (H1_9): There is a significant positive relationship between the existence of dedicated sustainability teams or departments and the intentions to embrace environmental sustainability practices in Egyptian enterprises.

10-Integration into Business Units

- Null Hypothesis (H0_10): There is no significant relationship between the integration of sustainability practices into business units and the intentions to embrace environmental sustainability practices in Egyptian enterprises.
- Alternative Hypothesis (H1_10): There is a significant positive relationship between the integration of sustainability practices into business units and the intentions to embrace environmental sustainability practices in Egyptian enterprises.

11-Sustainability Policies

- Null Hypothesis (H0_11): There is no significant relationship between the presence of formal sustainability policies and the intentions to embrace environmental sustainability practices in Egyptian enterprises.
- Alternative Hypothesis (H1_11): There is a significant positive relationship between the presence of formal sustainability policies and the intentions to embrace environmental sustainability practices in Egyptian enterprises.

12-Operational Practices

- Null Hypothesis (H0_12): There is no significant relationship between engagement in sustainable operational practices and the intentions to embrace environmental sustainability practices in Egyptian enterprises.
- Alternative Hypothesis (H1_12): There is a significant positive relationship between engagement in sustainable operational practices and the intentions to embrace environmental sustainability practices in Egyptian enterprises.

Research Methodology

Addressing these concerns, this research applies the Organizational Culture framework as a theoretical lens to investigate Egyptian corporates' intentions to adopt environmentally sustainable practices. Correlation analysis helps in understanding the relationship between various cultural dimensions, such as environmental values, leadership commitment, and employee engagement, and the intention to adopt sustainability practices. Regression analysis further elucidates the strength and nature of these relationships, offering insights into how strongly each cultural component influences sustainability adoption intentions. By understanding the factors that influence these companies' acceptance of sustainable practices, this study provides a roadmap for

Egyptian enterprises to navigate the complexities of integrating environmental sustainability into their operations.

By applying a comprehensive organizational culture model, the study sheds light on the factors that influence these companies' intentions to adopt sustainable practices.

Research Design:

This study explores the intricate relationship between the components of organizational culture and the intention to adopt environmental sustainability practices within Egyptian corporates. The focal point of this research is to examine how various dimensions of organizational culture, such as leadership commitment, employee engagement, and communication, influence sustainability intentions.

A deductive approach is applied, involving the testing of theoretical assertions related to organizational culture in the context of environmental sustainability. The research formulates hypotheses about how these cultural components might influence the intention to implement sustainability practices within Egyptian enterprises. By adopting a structured and methodical approach, this study investigates the role of organizational culture in shaping attitudes and intentions toward environmental sustainability.

Using deductive methodology, structured surveys, and statistical analysis, the study aims to provide valuable insights into how elements of organizational culture influence the desire to implement sustainable practices in Egyptian businesses.

Questionnaire Design:

In this comprehensive survey, designed to delve into the attitudes and intentions of professionals within Egyptian corporates regarding environmental sustainability practices, respondents are invited to engage with a series of thoughtfully constructed questions. This survey

aims to unravel the complex layers of organizational culture dimensions, including values and beliefs, leadership commitment, employee engagement, communication, organizational structure, and policies and practices, and their influence on the intention to adopt sustainable practices. Environmental Values and Beliefs: This section focuses on understanding whether environmental sustainability is perceived as a core value within the organization and if it is considered integral to improving the company's overall environmental performance.

Leadership Commitment and Employee Engagement: The survey seeks to assess the extent of leadership support for sustainability initiatives and the level of employee involvement and participation in sustainability practices. Communication and Transparency: Questions aim to evaluate the effectiveness of internal communication regarding sustainability goals and the transparency of reporting sustainability performance and impacts. Organizational Structure and Policy Integration:

The survey explores whether there are dedicated sustainability teams, and how sustainability practices are integrated into various business units and operational processes. Sustainability Policies and Operational Practices: This section investigates the presence and implementation of formal sustainability policies and their perceived effectiveness in enhancing environmental impact control and management.

By focusing on these key dimensions, the survey aims to provide valuable insights into how organizational culture influences the adoption and integration of sustainable practices within Egyptian enterprises. The survey results will be analyzed to determine the strength and nature of these relationships, offering guidance on how companies can enhance their organizational culture to better support environmental sustainability initiatives.

Sample Size

This decision is informed by the guidelines provided by Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2009), who suggest that a sample size of 39 is required to achieve a 95% confidence level with a 10% margin of error, given a target population of approximately 200. As Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill (2009) note, the non-probability judgement sampling technique involves the purposive or deliberate selection of specific units from the universe to constitute a sample that represents the entire population. It allows for a more targeted approach to sampling, where the researcher's judgement plays a crucial role in selecting cases that are deemed most representative or insightful for the research objectives. The chosen sample size of 39, informed by Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill's guidelines, is optimized for robust statistical analysis within the confines of a manageable research process.

Measurements and Data Collection Process:

The study variables were measured through adapted measurement scales from previous studies as summarized in Table 1:

Variable	Construct	Dimensions	source
Independent	Organizational Culture	Environmental Values	EV Dunlap, R. E., & Van Liere, K. D. (1978). Deshpande, R., & Webster, F. E. (1989).
		Cultural Norms	CN Schein, E. H. (1985). Hofstede, G., Hofstede, G. J., & Minkov, M. (2010).
		Top Management Support	TMS Epstein, M. J., & Buhovac, A. R. (2014). Doppelt, B. (2003).
		Vision and Mission Alignment	FMA Collins, J. C., & Porras, J. I. (1996).
		Involvement in Sustainability	ISI Ramus, C. A. (2001). Daily, B. F., & Huang, S. (2001).
		Training and Awareness Programs	TAP Jackson, S. E., Renwick, D. W. S., Jabbour, C. J. C., & Müller-Camen, M. (2011). Ramus, C. A., & Steger, U. (2000).
		Internal Communication	IC Lozano, R. (2013). Post, J. E., Preston, L. E., & Sachs, S. (2002).
		Transparency and Reporting	TR Adams, C. A., & McNicholas, P. (2007). Schallegger, S., & Wagner, M. (2006).
		Sustainability Departments	SD Epstein, M. J., & Roy, M. J. (2001).
		Integration into Business Units	IIBU Hart, S. L., & Milstein, M. B. (2003).
		Sustainability Policies	SP Aragon-Correa, J. A., & Sharma, S. (2003). Delmas, M. A., & Toffel, M. W. (2008).
		Operational Practices	OP Russo, M. V., & Fouts, P. A. (1997).
		Dependent	Intentions to Embrace Environmental Sustainability Practices

Table 1 Variables adapted measurement scales (Elaborated by the researcher).

Moreover, the Interval scale represented in a five-point Likert scale which was ranged from 5= strongly agree to 1= strongly disagree has been utilized to know the degree of respondents' agreement or disagreement with the proposed statements (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2009).

Questionnaire Administration

The questionnaire will be administered electronically using an online survey platform. Participants will receive an invitation containing a link to the survey.

Data Collection Timeline

The data collection period is estimated to be four to six weeks, allowing sufficient time for participants to respond.

Data Collection and Analysis

The primary objective of this analysis is to unravel the facts and data, thereby yielding insightful findings that contribute to the understanding of environmental sustainability practices within Egyptian corporates. The first step in the data analysis process involved ensuring the validity and reliability of the measuring scales used in the study, focusing on the dimensions of organizational culture. This step is crucial, as it ensures that the conclusions drawn from the study are based on reliable instruments. The results of the normality test inform the researcher about the appropriate statistical methods to use for further analysis. In the context of this study, multiple regression analysis was employed to investigate the relationships between various components of organizational culture such as environmental values, leadership commitment, employee engagement, and communication and the intention to adopt environmental sustainability practices in Egyptian

enterprises. Starting from ensuring the validity and reliability of the measuring instruments to conducting descriptive and inferential statistical analyses, each step has been carried out with meticulous attention to detail. This thorough approach helps in understanding how different aspects of organizational culture influence sustainability adoption intentions, providing a comprehensive framework for analyzing how these cultural factors shape environmental sustainability practices within the corporate sector in Egypt.

Demographic analysis

Demographic analysis is a method for measuring racial, ethnic, and age distributions as well as how these characteristics have changed over time because of the three main demographic processes: migration, fertility, and mortality (Lucas, D. 2002).

Gender, Age, and company size were the demographic factors measured in this research (Figure 2,3,4). Gender was classified as either male or female; there were 36 men and 3 females. There were three groups based on company size: small (4 occurrences), medium (12 occurrences), and Large (23 occurrences). The corresponding percentages are 15.4%, 28.2%, and 56.4%.

over 20
37 responses

Figure 2, Gender of responses pie charter. (Elaborated by the researcher)

Figure 3, Age of responses pie charter. (Elaborated by the researcher)

Figure 4 Company Size pie charters (Elaborated by the researcher)

Normality Test by Shapiro-Wilk

The Shapiro-Wilk test is a hypothesis test applied to a sample with the null hypothesis that the sample was generated from a normal distribution. If the p-value is low, we can reject this null hypothesis and say that the sample was not generated from a normal distribution.

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
independent_1	.172	39	.005	.899	39	.002
independent_2	.198	39	.000	.927	39	.015
independent_3	.241	39	.000	.877	39	.001
independent_4	.334	39	.000	.743	39	.000
independent_5	.179	39	.003	.906	39	.003
independent_6	.184	39	.002	.948	39	.073
independent_7	.167	39	.008	.912	39	.005
independent_8	.201	39	.000	.906	39	.003
independent_9	.242	39	.000	.895	39	.002
independent_10	.212	39	.000	.861	39	.000
independent_11	.168	39	.007	.923	39	.011
independent_12	.275	39	.000	.856	39	.000
dependent	.141	39	.048	.919	39	.008

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Table 2 normality test (Elaborated by the researcher based on SPSS results)

Table 2 shows that all of the variables' data substantially differ from a normal distribution, with p-values < 0.05 for every one of them. According to Razali and Wah (2011). The distribution of the sample means approaches a normal distribution as the sample size rises, according to the Central Limit Theorem, even for a population with any distribution. Using a normal distribution as an approximation works pretty well for samples with an n-size greater than 30. With increasing n, the approximation approaches a normal distribution more closely. We have n = 39 here (Fischer, H. 2011).

Reliability Test

A measuring system's consistency, stability, and reliability may be assessed statistically using reliability analysis.

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.913	13

Overall

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.918	20

organizational culture

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.905	5

Intentions to Embrace Environmental Sustainability Practices

Table 3 CRONBACH'S ALPHA (Elaborated by the researcher based on SPSS results)

Table 3 reveals that the data have high levels of internal consistency dependability, with a total Cronbach's alpha of 0.913. There is strong dependability and internal consistency among the 20 items on the dimensions of organizational culture, as indicated by Cronbach's alpha score of 0.918. The Intentions to Embrace Environmental Sustainability Practices dimensions have strong reliability and internal consistency with Cronbach's alpha rating of 0.905.

Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive statistics is a subfield of statistics concerned with providing clear and concise summaries, organization, and presentation of data. Without drawing broad inferences about the population, the emphasis is on characterizing and analyzing the essential characteristics of a dataset.

Descriptive Statistics									
scale	Discription	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance	
		Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Statistic
EV	Environmental Values	39	2	3	5	4.1667	0.09777	0.61058	0.373
CN	Cultural Norms	39	2.5	2.5	5	3.7692	0.0897	0.56015	0.314
TMS	Top Management Support	39	2	3	5	4.0385	0.0869	0.54271	0.295
FMA	Vision and Mission Alignment	39	3	2	5	4.1026	0.10256	0.64051	0.41
ISI	Involvement in Sustainability	39	4	1	5	3.5	0.12184	0.76089	0.579
TAP	Training and Awareness Programs	39	3.5	1.5	5	3.2692	0.12301	0.76817	0.59
IC	Internal Communication	39	4	1	5	3.3974	0.13644	0.85208	0.726
TR	Transparency and Reporting	39	4	1	5	3.359	0.12981	0.81069	0.657
SD	Sustainability Departments	39	4	1	5	3.4103	0.15463	0.96567	0.933
IIBU	Integration into Business Units	39	4	1	5	3.5641	0.15497	0.96777	0.937
SP	Sustainability Policies	39	4	1	5	3.5513	0.14439	0.90172	0.813
OP	Operational Practices	39	4	1	5	3.5385	0.15519	0.96916	0.939
IEESP	Intentions to Embrace Environmental Sustainability Practices	39	4	1	5	3.6462	0.11674	0.72904	0.531
	Valid N (listwise)	39							

Table 4 descriptive statistics (Elaborated by the researcher based on SPSS results)

Correlation analysis

A bivariate correlation study was performed on the variables listed in table 5. The Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) was used to quantify the strength of the linear relationship between the two variables, which are quantitative and are paired. A correlation coefficient between 0.90 and 1.00 indicates a very high level of positive correlation, while a correlation between 0.70 and 0.90 indicates a high level of positive correlation, 0.50 to 0.70 indicates a moderate level of positive

correlation, and a correlation between 0.30 and 0.50 indicates a low level of positive correlation.

Correlations

	independent_1	independent_2	independent_3	independent_4	independent_5	independent_6	independent_7	independent_8	independent_9	independent_10	independent_11	independent_12	dependent
independent_1	1	.539**	.437**	.460**	.142	.435**	.173	.328*	.149	.349*	.510**	.245	.526**
	Pearson Correlation	.000	.003	.002	.195	.003	.146	.021	.183	.015	.000	.067	.000
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39
independent_2	.539**	1	.593**	.471**	.401**	.500**	.321*	.491**	.131	.465**	.454**	.380**	.607**
	Pearson Correlation	.000	.000	.001	.006	.001	.023	.001	.213	.001	.002	.008	.000
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39
independent_3	.437**	.593**	1	.291*	.494**	.369**	.464**	.431**	.195	.559**	.453**	.585**	.674**
	Pearson Correlation	.003	.000	.036	.001	.010	.001	.003	.117	.000	.002	.000	.000
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39
independent_4	.460**	.471**	.291*	1	.162	.237	.213	.383**	.398**	.286*	.424**	.290*	.497**
	Pearson Correlation	.002	.001	.036	.162	.074	.097	.008	.006	.039	.004	.037	.001
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39
independent_5	.142	.401**	.494**	.162	1	.563**	.609**	.576**	.125	.679**	.479**	.553**	.446**
	Pearson Correlation	.195	.006	.001	.162	.000	.000	.000	.224	.000	.001	.000	.002
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39
independent_6	.435**	.500**	.369**	.237	.563**	1	.538**	.580**	.042	.498**	.511**	.436**	.414**
	Pearson Correlation	.003	.001	.010	.074	.000	.000	.000	.399	.001	.000	.003	.004
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39
independent_7	.173	.321*	.464**	.213	.609**	.538**	1	.712**	.324*	.535**	.658**	.626**	.668**
	Pearson Correlation	.146	.023	.001	.097	.000	.000	.000	.022	.000	.000	.000	.000
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39
independent_8	.328*	.491**	.431**	.383**	.576**	.580**	.712**	1	.328*	.624**	.613**	.602**	.657**
	Pearson Correlation	.021	.001	.003	.008	.000	.000	.000	.021	.000	.000	.000	.000
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39
independent_9	.149	.131	.195	.398**	.125	.042	.324*	.328*	1	.337*	.595**	.292*	.556**
	Pearson Correlation	.183	.213	.117	.006	.224	.399	.022	.021	.018	.000	.036	.000
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39
independent_10	.349*	.465**	.559**	.286*	.679**	.498**	.535**	.624**	.337*	1	.644**	.565**	.686**
	Pearson Correlation	.015	.001	.000	.039	.000	.001	.000	.018	.000	.000	.000	.000
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39
independent_11	.510**	.454**	.453**	.424**	.479**	.511**	.658**	.613**	.595**	.644**	1	.585**	.825**
	Pearson Correlation	.000	.002	.002	.004	.001	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39
independent_12	.245	.380**	.585**	.290*	.553**	.436**	.626**	.602**	.292*	.565**	.585**	1	.679**
	Pearson Correlation	.067	.008	.000	.037	.000	.003	.000	.036	.000	.000	.000	.000
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39
dependent	.526**	.607**	.674**	.497**	.446**	.414**	.686**	.657**	.556**	.686**	.825**	.679**	1
	Pearson Correlation	.000	.000	.000	.001	.002	.004	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39	.39

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (1-tailed).

Table 5 correlation analysis (Elaborated by the researcher based on SPSS results)

Hypothesis 1:

there is a significant positive relationship between Environmental Values (independent variable) and Intentions to Embrace Environmental Sustainability Practices (dependent variable), the P value explored from the table is { $P = .000 < 0.01, r = 0.526$ }.

Hypothesis 2:

there is a significant positive relationship between Cultural Norms (independent variable) and Intentions to Embrace Environmental Sustainability Practices (dependent variable), the P value explored from the table is $\{P = .000 < 0.01, r = 0.607\}$.

Hypothesis 3:

there is a significant positive relationship between Top Management Support (independent variable) and Intentions to Embrace Environmental Sustainability Practices (dependent variable), the P value explored from the table is $\{P = .000 < 0.01, r = 0.674\}$.

Hypothesis 4:

there is a significant positive relationship between Vision and Mission Alignment (independent variable) and Intentions to Embrace Environmental Sustainability Practices (dependent variable), the P value explored from the table is $\{P = .000 < 0.01, r = 0.497\}$.

Hypothesis 5:

there is a significant positive relationship between Involvement in Sustainability (independent variable) and Intentions to Embrace Environmental Sustainability Practices (dependent variable), the P value explored from the table is $\{P = .000 < 0.01, r = 0.446\}$.

Hypothesis 6:

there is a significant positive relationship between Training and Awareness Programs (independent variable) and Intentions to Embrace Environmental Sustainability Practices (dependent variable), the P value explored from the table is $\{P = .000 < 0.01, r = 0.414\}$.

Hypothesis 7:

there is a significant positive relationship between Internal Communication (independent variable) and Intentions to Embrace Environmental Sustainability Practices (dependent variable), the P value explored from the table is $\{P = .000 < 0.01, r = 0.686\}$.

Hypothesis 8:

there is a significant positive relationship between Transparency and Reporting (independent variable) and Intentions to Embrace Environmental Sustainability Practices (dependent variable), the P value explored from the table is $\{P = .000 < 0.01, r = 0.657\}$.

Hypothesis 9:

there is a significant positive relationship between Sustainability Departments (independent variable) and Intentions to Embrace Environmental Sustainability Practices (dependent variable), the P value explored from the table is $\{P = .000 < 0.01, r = 0.556\}$.

Hypothesis 10:

there is a significant positive relationship between Integration into Business Units (independent variable) and Intentions to Embrace Environmental Sustainability Practices (dependent variable), the P value explored from the table is $\{P = .000 < 0.01, r = 0.686\}$.

Hypothesis 11:

there is a significant positive relationship between Sustainability Policies (independent variable) and Intentions to Embrace Environmental Sustainability Practices (dependent variable), the P value explored from the table is $\{P = .000 < 0.01, r = 0.825\}$.

Hypothesis 12:

there is a significant positive relationship between Operational Practices (independent variable) and Intentions to Embrace Environmental Sustainability Practices (dependent variable), the P value explored from the table is $\{P = .000 < 0.01, r = 0.679\}$.

Regression Analysis

Linear regression analysis has been conducted for each explanatory or independent variables with the response or dependent variable to analysis and predict the relationship between these two variables. It assumes a linear relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable and aims to find the best fitting line that describes this relationship. Linear regression shows a linear relationship

between the independent (predictor) variable, which represents the x-axis, and the dependent (output) variable, which represents the y-axis. To calculate the line of best fit, linear regression uses the traditional slope-intercept form the equation: $(Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_i)$ where Y_i = dependent variable, β_0 = constant/origin, β_1 = slope/origin, X_i = independent variable.

Hypothesis 1:

Using data elaborated in the following tables 6. It refers that a one unit increase in explanatory will increase response by 27.7 %. Moreover, (R^2) is used to evaluate the model fit, generally, the model is considered fit when R^2 equals to 0.10 or higher (Falk & Miller, 1992). Giving the regression equation $(Y = 1.029 + 0.628 X)$

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.526(a)	.277	.257	.62829	.277	14.164	1	37	.001

a Predictors: (Constant), independent_1

Coefficients(a)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error				Beta	Lower Bound
1	(Constant)	1.029	.703		1.464	.152	-.395	2.452
	independent_1	.628	.167	.526	3.764	.001	.290	.966

a Dependent Variable: dependent

Table 6 regression model summary H1

Hypothesis 2:

Using data elaborated in the following tables 7. It refers that a one unit increase in explanatory will increase response by 36.8 %. Giving the regression equation ($Y = 1.029 + 0.628 X$)

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.607(a)	.368	.351	.58729	.368	21.556	1	37	.000

a Predictors: (Constant), independent_2

Coefficients(a)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	.670	.648		1.034	.308	-.643	1.983
	independent_2	.790	.170	.607	4.643	.000	.445	1.134

a Dependent Variable: dependent

Table 7 regression model summary H2

Hypothesis 3:

Using data elaborated in the following tables 8. It refers that a one unit increase in explanatory will increase response by 45.4 %. Giving the regression equation ($Y = 0.009 + 0.905 X$)

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.674(a)	.454	.439	.54592	.454	30.769	1	37	.000

a Predictors: (Constant), independent_3

Coefficients(a)

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1 (Constant)	-.009	.665		-.014	.989	-1.356	1.338
independent_3	.905	.163	.674	5.547	.000	.575	1.236

a Dependent Variable: dependent

Table 8 regression model summary H3

Hypothesis 4:

Using data elaborated in the following tables 9. It refers that a one unit increase in explanatory will increase response by 24.7 %. Giving the regression equation ($Y = 1.326 + 0.565 X$)

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.497(a)	.247	.226	.64120	.247	12.124	1	37	.001

a Predictors: (Constant), independent_4

Coefficients(a)

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1 (Constant)	1.326	.674		1.968	.057	-.040	2.692
independent_4	.565	.162	.497	3.482	.001	.236	.895

a Dependent Variable: dependent

Table 9 regression model summary H4

Hypothesis 5:

Using data elaborated in the following tables 10. It refers that a one unit increase in explanatory will increase response by 19.9%. Giving the regression equation ($Y = 2.151 + 0.427 X$)

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.446(a)	.199	.177	.66130	.199	9.184	1	37	.004

a Predictors: (Constant), independent_5

Coefficients(a)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	2.151	.505		4.261	.000	1.128	3.173
	independent_5	.427	.141	.446	3.031	.004	.142	.713

a Dependent Variable: dependent

Table 10 regression model summary H5

Hypothesis 6:

Using data elaborated in the following tables 11. It refers that a one unit increase in explanatory will increase response by 17.2%. Giving the regression equation ($Y = 2.361 + 0.393 X$)

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.414(a)	.172	.149	.67246	.172	7.664	1	37	.009

a Predictors: (Constant), independent_6

Coefficients(a)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	2.361	.477		4.954	.000	1.395	3.327
	independent_6	.393	.142	.414	2.768	.009	.105	.681

a Dependent Variable: dependent

Table 11 regression model summary H6

Hypothesis 7:

Using data elaborated in the following tables 12. It refers that a one unit increase in explanatory will increase response by 47%. Giving the regression equation ($Y = 1.653 + 0.587 X$)

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.686(a)	.470	.456	.53783	.470	32.822	1	37	.000

a Pr **Coefficients(a)**

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error				Beta	Lower Bound
1	(Constant)	1.653	.358		4.613	.000	.927	2.379
	independent_7	.587	.102	.686	5.729	.000	.379	.794

a Dependent Variable: dependent

Table 12 regression model summary H7

Hypothesis 8:

Using data elaborated in the following tables 13. It refers that a one unit increase in explanatory will increase response by 43.2%. Giving the regression equation ($Y = 1.662 + 0.591 X$)

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.657(a)	.432	.416	.55704	.432	28.089	1	37	.000

a Predictors: (Constant), independent_8

Coefficients(a)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	1.662	.385		4.318	.000	.882	2.442
	independent_t_8	.591	.111	.657	5.300	.000	.365	.817

a Dependent Variable: dependent

Table 13 regression model summary H8

Hypothesis 9:

Using data elaborated in the following tables 14. It refers that a one unit increase in explanatory will increase response by 30.9%. Giving the regression equation ($Y = 2.216 + 0.419 X$)

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.556(a)	.309	.290	.61434	.309	16.515	1	37	.000

a Predictors: (Constant), independent_9

Coefficients(a)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	2.216	.365		6.064	.000	1.475	2.956
	independent_9	.419	.103	.556	4.064	.000	.210	.628

a Dependent Variable: dependent

Table 14 regression model summary H9

Hypothesis 10:

Using data elaborated in the following tables 15. It refers that a one unit increase in explanatory will increase response by 47%. Giving the regression equation ($Y = 1.805 + 0.517 X$)

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.686(a)	.470	.456	.53776	.470	32.840	1	37	.000

a Predictors: (Constant), independent_10

Coefficients(a)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
		Beta						
1	(Constant)	1.805	.333		5.427	.000	1.131	2.479
	independent_10	.517	.090	.686	5.731	.000	.334	.699

a Dependent Variable: dependent

Table 15 regression model summary H10

Hypothesis 11:

Using data elaborated in the following tables 16. It refers that a one unit increase in explanatory will increase response by 68.1%. Giving the regression equation ($Y = 1.278 + 0.667 X$)

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.825(a)	.681	.672	.41759	.681	78.819	1	37	.000

a Predictors: (Constant), independent_11

Coefficients(a)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	1.278	.275		4.645	.000	.720	1.835
	independent_11	.667	.075	.825	8.878	.000	.515	.819

a Dependent Variable: dependent

Table 16 regression model summary H11

Hypothesis 12:

Using data elaborated in the following tables 17. It refers that a one unit increase in explanatory will increase response by 46.1%. Giving the regression equation ($Y = 1.839 + 0.511 X$)

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.679(a)	.461	.446	.54239	.461	31.652	1	37	.000

a Predictors: (Constant), independent_12

Coefficients(a)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	1.839	.333		5.526	.000	1.165	2.513
	independent_12	.511	.091	.679	5.626	.000	.327	.695

a Dependent Variable: dependent

Table 17 regression model summary H12

Multiple Regression Analysis

Both the Sustainability Policies and the Top Management Support, which are selected explanatory factors, and the response variable, Intentions to Embrace Environmental Sustainability Practices, is the dependent variable in a multiple regression analysis.

Tables 18 provide the full results of the best fit multiple regression model, which shows that Sustainability Policies is the most important variable (68.1% of the total) and that Top Management Support is the second most important (11.3%).

Considering the total R2 value in model 2 reveals that both have a 79.4% impact on Intentions to Embrace Environmental Sustainability Practices, indicating the optimal multiple regression model. $Y = 0.280 + 0.529 X1 + 0.507 X2$ is the regression equation that provides the relationship between Intentions to Embrace Environmental Sustainability Practices, Sustainability Policies (X1), and Top Management Support (X2). The results show that the residuals follow a distribution that is close to normal (Figures 5&6).

Model Summary(c)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.825(a)	.681	.672	.41759	.681	78.819	1	37	.000	
2	.891(b)	.794	.782	.34005	.113	19.797	1	36	.000	2.311

a Predictors: (Constant), independent_11

b Predictors: (Constant), independent_11, independent_3

c Dependent Variable: dependent

Coefficients(a)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	1.278	.275		4.645	.000	.720	1.835
	independent _11	.667	.075	.825	8.878	.000	.515	.819
2	(Constant)	-.280	.416		-.674	.505	-1.123	.563
	independent _11	.529	.069	.654	7.704	.000	.390	.668
	independent _3	.507	.114	.378	4.449	.000	.276	.739

a Dependent Variable: dependent
 Table 18 model summary of multiple regression

Histogram

Figure 5 model histogram

Normal P-P Plot of Regression Standardized Residual

Figure 6 model P-P plot

Discussion

Correlation Analysis

The study conducted a bivariate correlation analysis using Pearson's correlation coefficient to measure the linear relationships between organizational culture dimensions and the intentions to embrace environmental sustainability practices. Results from Table 5 indicate varying strengths of correlation: Environmental Values ($r = 0.526$) showed a moderate positive correlation with intentions to embrace sustainability practices, suggesting a reasonable link between these values and sustainability actions. Cultural Norms ($r = 0.607$) and Top Management Support ($r = 0.674$) both exhibited high positive correlations, indicating strong influences on sustainability intentions, reflecting the critical role of cultural attitudes and leadership in promoting sustainability. Vision and Mission Alignment ($r = 0.497$) and

Involvement in Sustainability ($r = 0.446$) demonstrated lower yet significant positive correlations, suggesting that while important, they are among the lesser predictors compared to other variables. Training and Awareness Programs ($r = 0.414$), Internal Communication ($r = 0.686$), and Transparency and Reporting ($r = 0.657$) also showed significant correlations, with Internal Communication being particularly strong, emphasizing the importance of clear, consistent communication in fostering sustainability practices. Sustainability Departments ($r = 0.556$), Integration into Business Units ($r = 0.686$), Sustainability Policies ($r = 0.825$), and Operational Practices ($r = 0.679$) displayed high to very high correlations, particularly Sustainability Policies, which suggests that formal policies are highly effective in promoting sustainability intentions.

Regression Analysis

Linear regression analysis further explored the relationships between these variables. Key findings include: A one-unit increase in Sustainability Policies is associated with a significant increase in the intentions to embrace sustainability practices, with the highest impact among all tested variables (68.1%). Top Management Support also significantly increases sustainability intentions, reinforcing the importance of leadership in driving sustainability efforts. The regression models consistently showed significant positive effects across all variables on sustainability intentions, confirming the predictive power of organizational culture dimensions on sustainability actions. The model summaries provide the equations and statistics necessary to predict how changes in these cultural dimensions affect sustainability intentions, with R^2 values indicating good model fits, particularly when combined variables like Sustainability Policies and Top Management Support are considered.

This comprehensive analysis highlights the substantial impact of various facets of organizational culture on the sustainability practices within corporations, particularly in Egyptian contexts. The findings not

only support the hypotheses but also offer actionable insights for organizations looking to enhance their sustainability initiatives.

Conclusions

This research underscores the significant influence of organizational culture on the intention to embrace environmental sustainability practices in Egyptian enterprises. Among the twelve dimensions examined, sustainability policies and top management support are identified as the most impactful, highlighting the importance of strategic alignment and leadership in driving sustainability initiatives. Theoretical contributions of this study include a deeper understanding of the cultural dimensions influencing sustainability within a specific geographical context. Practically, the findings offer actionable insights for organizations to cultivate a culture that supports sustainable practices. By focusing on robust sustainability policies and strong top management support, companies can enhance their sustainability efforts and achieve long-term success.

Theoretical Implications

The study enriches the theoretical discourse on organizational culture and sustainability by identifying key cultural dimensions that drive sustainable practices. It highlights the role of strategic leadership and formal policies in shaping organizational behaviors and intentions towards sustainability.

Practical Implications

Practically, this research provides actionable strategies for Egyptian businesses to strengthen their sustainability initiatives. By prioritizing sustainability policies and top management support, organizations can create a supportive cultural environment that fosters sustainability and enhances competitive advantage.

Areas for Future Research

Future research could delve into the impact of digital transformation on organizational culture and sustainability, as well as conduct comparative studies across different cultural and economic contexts to broaden the applicability of the findings.

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